

**EVALUATION OF THE USE OF CONTRACEPTIVES AMONG FEMALE STUDENTS
AT THE UNIVERSITY OF ABUJA**

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the use of contraceptives among female students at the University of Abuja, focusing on their knowledge, attitudes, and factors influencing contraceptive use. The research explores the types of contraceptives commonly used, the level of awareness regarding their effectiveness, and the barriers to consistent use. A cross-sectional survey design was employed, with questionnaires administered to a sample of female students across various faculties. Data analysis revealed that while the majority of respondents had basic knowledge of contraceptives, misconceptions and social stigma remain significant barriers to effective use. The study highlighted the role of education, accessibility, and peer influence in shaping contraceptive behaviours. Recommendations include enhanced health education programs and the need for accessible reproductive health services to promote informed decision-making. This research contributes to understanding the reproductive health needs of female students and offers strategies to improve contraceptive uptake and safe practices.

KEYWORDS: Contraceptives, Behaviour, Female, Influence Awareness, Attitude

INTRODUCTION

The use of contraceptives has become an essential aspect of reproductive health management worldwide, especially among sexually active individuals. Globally, the importance of contraceptive use in preventing unintended pregnancies and reducing the risks associated with unsafe abortions is well-documented (World Health Organization, 2020).

In many parts of the world, especially in Sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria, the adoption of contraceptive methods has been emphasized in various health policies and programs. The need for widespread contraceptive use is more pressing due to high rates of unintended pregnancies, maternal mortality, and unsafe abortion practices (National Population Commission, 2018).

The World Health Organization (2020) highlighted that contraception plays a vital role in family planning, allowing individuals to determine the timing and spacing of their pregnancies, thereby improving maternal and child health outcomes. Contraceptives are crucial component of reproductive health management and have long been recognized as essential in preventing unintended pregnancies and reducing the risks associated with unsafe abortions. Globally, contraceptive use has proven to be an effective means of controlling fertility rates, empowering women, and promoting public health.

According to Sedgh, Singh & Hussain (2017), in developing regions like Sub-Saharan Africa, reproductive health programs have emphasized the need for modern contraceptive methods as a way to curb population growth, improve women's health, and support economic development.

Nigeria, as Africa's most populous country, faces unique challenges in implementing effective family planning programs. Despite various government initiatives, such as the National Family Planning Campaign and policies aimed at increasing the use of modern contraceptives, the contraceptive prevalence rate remains low, particularly among young people. This is due in part to cultural and religious beliefs that stigmatize contraceptive use, a lack of comprehensive sexual education, and misconceptions about the safety and efficacy of contraception (Ijadunola, Abiona & Oyeniran, 2018).

Adebowale, et al (2019) noted that young women, particularly those in tertiary institutions, represent a key demographic for the promotion of contraceptive use. As they transition into adulthood, they are more likely to engage in sexual activities, often without adequate knowledge or resources to protect themselves from unintended pregnancies and sexually transmitted infections (STIs). Studies have shown that young women in universities face various challenges that influence their sexual behavior, including peer pressure, a newfound sense of independence, and inadequate sexual education. For many female students, the decision to use contraceptives is shaped by multiple factors, including the availability of information, accessibility to healthcare services, and the influence of cultural, religious, and social norms.

Cultural context often plays a significant role in shaping attitudes towards contraceptive use in Nigeria. Many young women report that they are discouraged from using contraceptives due to societal expectations about premarital abstinence, religious beliefs that oppose contraception, and fears about the side effects of contraceptives (Chigbu, Ogu & Umeora, 2021).

Research by Akinyemi, Omoluabi & Tsui (2020) indicates that despite the availability of modern contraceptives, many young women remain skeptical about their safety and effectiveness, with some relying on traditional methods or withdrawal, which are less reliable. As a result, many female students either do not use contraceptives at all or use them inconsistently, increasing their risk of unintended pregnancies and unsafe abortions.

The use of contraceptives among female students is influenced by a wide range of factors, including their level of education, socio-economic status, access to healthcare services, and the quality of sexual and reproductive health information they receive. According to Ijadunola, Abiona & Oyeniran (2018), knowledge about contraceptives is a critical determinant of whether young women will adopt family planning methods. However, studies have shown that even when female students are aware of contraceptive methods, they may still be influenced by myths and

misconceptions about their effects on fertility and health. For example, many young women believe that contraceptives cause infertility or serious side effects, which discourages them from using them consistently or at all.

Moreover, the availability and accessibility of contraceptive services also play a significant role in determining contraceptive use. In many universities, including the University of Abuja, there is limited access to affordable and confidential reproductive health services, making it difficult for female students to obtain contraceptives when they need them. Additionally, social stigma surrounding contraceptive use often deters young women from seeking out family planning services (Chigbu, et al., 2021).

A study by Akinyemi, et al., (2020) found that many students fear being judged by healthcare providers or peers if they are seen seeking contraceptives, particularly in conservative or religious communities where premarital sexual activity is discouraged.

Education plays a vital role in shaping attitudes and behaviors related to contraceptive use. Research has shown that young women who receive comprehensive sexual education are more likely to use contraceptives and make informed decisions about their reproductive health (Ezeanolue, Gbadamosi & Iwelunmor, 2017). In Nigeria, however, sexual education remains inadequate, particularly in secondary schools and universities. Many students enter university with little to no formal education about contraception, relying instead on information from peers, the internet, or traditional sources, which may not always be accurate. This lack of reliable information can lead to poor decision-making and increased vulnerability to unintended pregnancies (Chigbu, et al., 2021).

This study thus seeks to evaluate the use of contraceptives among female students at the University of Abuja.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Despite global and national efforts to promote contraceptive use, there remains a pressing need for targeted interventions to improve sexual and reproductive health education among female students at the University of Abuja. Many students lack access to adequate information and resources to make informed decisions regarding contraceptive use, leading to high rates of unintended pregnancies and unsafe abortions.

Ezeanolue, et al. (2017) emphasized that universities can play a pivotal role in addressing this issue by incorporating sexual and reproductive health education into the curriculum and providing students with workshops and counseling services. Such initiatives would empower female students with the knowledge and resources needed to navigate their reproductive health effectively.

On a global scale, various international organizations, such as the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) and the World Health Organization (WHO), have implemented initiatives aimed at increasing the use of modern contraceptives, particularly in developing regions like Sub-Saharan Africa. These efforts are crucial in addressing the unmet need for contraception, which remains alarmingly high in many parts of the world (WHO, 2020). Despite these efforts, many young women in Nigeria still face significant barriers to accessing contraceptive services.

In Nigeria, government policies such as the National Reproductive Health Policy and Strategy (2001) and the Nigeria Family Planning Blueprint (2014) have been designed to promote contraceptive use and reduce maternal mortality (National Population Commission, 2018). These initiatives aim to improve access to family planning services and raise public awareness about the benefits of contraception. However, substantial obstacles persist, including limited funding for reproductive health services, cultural and religious opposition to family planning, and inadequate health infrastructure (Sedgh, et al., 2017). These barriers are particularly pronounced in university settings, where young women often struggle to access confidential and affordable reproductive health services.

At the University of Abuja, addressing these barriers is critical to reducing the incidence of unintended pregnancies and improving the overall well-being of female students. Without proper education and accessible services, students are left vulnerable to the consequences of inadequate contraceptive use, highlighting the urgent need for comprehensive interventions in this area. In addition, there is a need for targeted interventions aimed at improving sexual and reproductive health education among female students. This could include workshops, counseling services, and the integration of reproductive health education into the university curriculum.

Ezeanolue, et al. (2017) maintained that by providing female students with the knowledge and resources they need to make informed decisions, the university can play a crucial role in promoting contraceptive use and reducing the incidence of unintended pregnancies and unsafe abortions.

Globally, significant efforts have been made to increase the use of modern contraceptives, particularly among young women in developing countries. International organizations such as the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) and the World Health Organization (WHO) have launched various initiatives aimed at promoting family planning and improving access to contraceptive services. These efforts have been particularly focused on Sub-Saharan Africa, where the unmet need for contraception remains high (WHO, 2020).

In Nigeria, the government has implemented several policies and programs to promote contraceptive use, including the National Reproductive Health Policy and Strategy (2001) and the Nigeria Family Planning Blueprint (2014) (National Population Commission, 2018). These policies aim to increase the contraceptive prevalence rate and reduce the incidence of maternal mortality by improving access to family planning services and educating the public about the benefits of contraception. However, despite these efforts, significant barriers remain, including limited funding for reproductive health services, cultural resistance to family planning, and inadequate health infrastructure (Sedgh, et al., 2017).

1.3 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The findings of this study will be of benefit to the followings:

- ❖ **Public Health Professionals:** This study is highly relevant to public health, as it addresses the pressing issue of contraceptive use among young women, particularly female students at the University of Abuja. The findings will provide valuable data on the current status of contraceptive use, highlighting areas where improvements can be made to promote sexual and reproductive health among this vulnerable population. Understanding the factors that influence

contraceptive use, such as knowledge, access, cultural beliefs, and healthcare services, can lead to more effective public health interventions. By addressing these gaps, the study contributes to efforts aimed at reducing unintended pregnancies and their associated health risks, including unsafe abortions and maternal complications (World Health Organization, 2020).

- ❖ **Policy Makers:** The insights from this study can play a significant role in shaping national and institutional policy. Policymakers at both the national and university levels can use the findings to develop comprehensive strategies for improving access to contraceptives and ensuring that female students receive adequate sexual and reproductive health education. The study's data will be useful in evaluating the effectiveness of existing policies and identifying gaps in the implementation of reproductive health programs. This information will enable policymakers to make evidence-based decisions that can lead to more inclusive, youth-friendly health services (National Population Commission, 2018).
- ❖ **Campus-Based Reproductive Health Programs:** This study's results can directly influence the development of campus-based reproductive health initiatives at the University of Abuja and other similar institutions. University administrators can use the findings to design programs that address the specific reproductive health needs of female students, incorporating both education and service delivery aspects. By understanding the barriers to contraceptive use—whether they are related to cultural misconceptions, lack of access to services, or insufficient knowledge—administrators can create targeted interventions such as awareness campaigns, peer education programs, or partnerships with local healthcare providers to ensure students receive comprehensive care (Chigbu, et al., 2021).
- ❖ **Improving Academic Success and Student Well-Being:** Unintended pregnancies can have a significant negative impact on the academic success and overall well-being of female students. Many young women who experience unintended pregnancies may face challenges such as financial strain, social stigma, and the need to drop out of school temporarily or permanently (Sedgh et al., 2017). By promoting effective contraceptive use, this study can contribute to reducing these disruptions, enabling students to focus on their academic goals and maintain their mental and physical health. The availability of reliable contraceptive methods and related healthcare services on campus can empower students to make informed choices about their reproductive health, ultimately supporting their educational pursuits and long-term success.
- ❖ **Contribution to Existing Literature:** The study will also contribute to the body of academic literature on contraceptive use in Nigeria, particularly within the context of higher education institutions. There is a need for more research focusing on the unique reproductive health challenges faced by female university students, as many studies on contraceptive use in Nigeria have focused on broader populations or specific community settings (Adebowale, et al., 2019). By filling this gap, the research will provide future scholars and health practitioners with detailed data and analysis that can inform further studies and interventions aimed at improving sexual and reproductive health outcomes in tertiary institutions.

2.0 CONTRACEPTIVE USE IN NIGERIA

The rate of contraceptive use in Nigeria remains critically low, particularly among young women and students. According to the National Population Commission (2018), only 12% of women of reproductive age (15-49) use modern contraceptive methods. This low rate is influenced by a range of factors including cultural norms, lack of education, access to reproductive health services, and persistent misconceptions about contraceptives.

Cultural and religious factors are prominent determinants of contraceptive use in Nigeria. In many parts of the country, contraceptive use is seen as taboo, particularly for unmarried women (Okonofua et al., 2016). Adebowale, et al (2019) also reported that cultural beliefs often link contraception with promiscuity, discouraging young women from using birth control methods. These beliefs are further reinforced by religious teachings, particularly in conservative Christian and Islamic communities, which promote abstinence over contraceptive use (Ijadunola, et al., 2018).

A study by Oyediran and Ishola (2018) highlighted that cultural resistance to contraceptive use in Northern Nigeria is partly rooted in the societal emphasis on large families, which are often seen as a source of wealth and social security. In contrast, in Southern Nigeria, there is a slightly higher acceptance of contraceptive use, although young women still face significant barriers, particularly regarding stigma and misinformation.

According to the study by Aina (2019), many Nigerian women, especially those in rural areas, struggle to access reproductive health services due to a lack of healthcare facilities, high cost of contraceptives, and long distances to clinics which Melka, et al, (2018) opined are further exacerbated by the social stigma surrounding contraception, which deters young women from seeking out family planning services

In addition to physical barriers, women in Nigeria also face challenges related to the quality of care provided by healthcare providers. A study by Adebowale, et al. (2019) revealed that many women reported feeling judged by healthcare providers when seeking contraceptive services. This sentiment is particularly pronounced among unmarried young women, who fear being labeled as promiscuous or immoral. As a result, many women opt for less reliable methods or avoid contraceptives altogether.

Misconceptions and myths about contraceptive use are pervasive in Nigeria, significantly affecting uptake. A survey by Ezeanolue, et al. (2017) found that a large proportion of Nigerian women believed that modern contraceptives could cause long-term health problems, including infertility, cancer, and birth defects. Such misconceptions were found to be prevalent even among university students, where education levels are higher.

These misconceptions are fueled by inadequate sexual health education, both at the family and school levels. According to Okonofua, et al. (2016), many Nigerian schools do not offer comprehensive sex education, and discussions about reproductive health are often limited to abstinence, particularly in religious institutions. As a result, many young women rely on informal

sources of information, such as friends or the internet, which may perpetuate incorrect beliefs about contraceptives (Ijadunola, et al., 2018).

2.1 CONTRACEPTIVE USE AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

University students, particularly female students, are at a critical stage where reproductive health education and access to contraceptives can significantly impact their future health and socio-economic outcomes. Despite their relatively higher education levels compared to the general population, many female university students in Nigeria still face significant barriers to accessing and using contraceptives.

Studies consistently show a gap between awareness of contraceptives and actual usage among female university students in Nigeria. In a study conducted at the University of Lagos, Ojediran and Odujirin (2017) found that while 68% of female students were aware of modern contraceptive methods, only 38% reported regular use. This disparity highlights the fact that awareness does not necessarily translate into behavior change, particularly when other barriers such as fear of side effects, social stigma, and limited access to services are present.

Similarly, a study by Chigbu, et al. (2021) on contraceptive use among female university students in South-East Nigeria reported widespread knowledge of contraceptives, but actual use remained low. Only 29% of respondents were using contraceptives regularly, with many citing concerns about potential side effects, fear of being judged by healthcare providers, and misinformation about contraceptive methods as reasons for non-use.

At the University of Abuja, there is a dearth of comprehensive data on contraceptive use among female students, but anecdotal evidence suggests that similar factors may be at play. A report by the Nigerian Institute of Medical Research (2020) noted that many female students at the university expressed concerns about social stigma and the quality of available reproductive health services. As a result, many students either do not use contraceptives or rely on less effective traditional methods.

Social stigma remains one of the most significant barriers to contraceptive use among female university students in Nigeria. In a study conducted at Obafemi Awolowo University, Adebowale et al. (2019) found that many female students felt embarrassed or ashamed to be seen accessing contraceptive services. This stigma is particularly pronounced among unmarried students, who are often judged harshly for being sexually active.

Peer influence also plays a crucial role in shaping contraceptive behaviors among university students. According to a study by Aina (2019), female students who perceived their peers as supportive of contraceptive use were more likely to use contraceptives themselves. Conversely, those who feared negative judgment from their friends or classmates were less likely to seek out contraceptive services. These dynamic highlights the importance of peer education programs in promoting contraceptive use among university students.

Access to reproductive health services is a key determinant of contraceptive use among female university students. Many Nigerian universities, particularly public institutions, do not offer comprehensive reproductive health services on campus (Chigbu, et al., 2021). Students often have

to travel off-campus to access family planning services, which can be a significant barrier, particularly for those without reliable transportation or financial resources.

A study conducted at the University of Ibadan by Adeoye (2018) found that the majority of students who used contraceptives obtained them from off-campus pharmacies or private clinics, rather than from university health centers. This finding suggests that there may be a need for more accessible on-campus reproductive health services, including family planning counseling and the provision of contraceptives.

Despite being in an academic environment, many university students in Nigeria continue to hold misconceptions about contraceptives. According to Ezeanolue, et al. (2017), this is partly due to the lack of comprehensive sexual health education within Nigerian universities. While some universities offer general health education courses, these often do not include detailed information about reproductive health and contraception.

The study by Chigbu, et al. (2021) found that many female students relied on their peers or social media for information about contraceptives, leading to the spread of misinformation. For instance, some students believed that contraceptives could cause infertility or reduce their chances of getting pregnant in the future. Such misconceptions often deter students from using contraceptives, even when they are sexually active and at risk of unintended pregnancies.

2.2 CONTRACEPTIVE USE AMONG FEMALE STUDENTS AT THE UNIVERSITY OF ABUJA

Though there are limited empirical perspectives specifically addressing contraceptive use among female students at the University of Abuja, the findings from other Nigerian universities can offer valuable insights into the factors that may be influencing students at this institution as Ijadunola, et al. (2018) averred that though most students were aware of modern contraceptive methods, only a minority used them consistently.

Though there are limited empirical highlights on the use of contraceptives among female students in northern Nigeria, several key factors that influence contraceptive use among female university students in Nigeria, including cultural and religious norms, social stigma, misconceptions about contraceptives, and limited access to reproductive health services.

It is therefore the intention of this study to evaluate the use of contraceptives among female students of the university of Abuja as it could provide an understanding of the general use of contraceptives among female university students in northern Nigeria.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

The study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional survey design, which is ideal for evaluating the contraceptive use patterns among female students at the University of Abuja. A descriptive survey design is appropriate because it allows for the collection of data at a single point in time, providing

a snapshot of contraceptive use among the study population. This design also enables the researcher to assess the prevalence of contraceptive use, as well as to explore the factors influencing students' contraceptive choices.

The study utilizes both qualitative and quantitative methods to gather comprehensive data. Quantitative methods were used to gather data on the prevalence of contraceptive use, while qualitative methods are employed to explore the factors that influence the decision-making process regarding contraceptive use among female students. This mixed-methods approach enables a more holistic understanding of the issue.

3.2 POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The study population comprises female students of the University of Abuja enrolled in various undergraduate programs. The choice of female students is based on the fact that they are the primary demographic group for evaluating contraceptive use within the university setting. Female students are more likely to engage in sexual activity while also being at risk of unintended pregnancies, making them an important group for studying contraceptive behavior.

The University of Abuja has a diverse student body, with students from various socio-economic, cultural, and educational backgrounds, making it an appropriate setting for exploring contraceptive use among a heterogeneous group of young women. The population includes students from different faculties such as the Faculties of Education, Social Sciences, Science, Arts, Health Sciences, Engineering etc

3.3 SAMPLE SIZE AND SAMPLING PROCEDURE

A stratified random sampling technique was used to select participants from different faculties within the university. This technique was adopted to ensure that the sample accurately represents the diverse academic disciplines within the university, as contraceptive use may differ based on factors such as field of study and exposure to reproductive health education.

- ❖ **Stratification:** The University of Abuja was divided into different strata based on the academic faculties (e.g., Education, Social Sciences, Natural Sciences, Arts, and Engineering). This stratification ensured that students from each faculty are adequately represented.
- ❖ **Random Selection:** Within each stratum, a random sample of female students was used to select participants in the study. This eliminates selection bias and ensure the sample is representative of a broader student population.

Based on an estimated population of 10,000 female students at the University of Abuja, and assuming a confidence level of 95% and a margin of error of 5%, the calculated sample size is approximately 250 female students.

❖ Inclusion And Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria: Female students enrolled at the University of Abuja during the period of the study.

- Female students who are 18 years and above.

- Female students who are sexually active or have had sexual experience.
- Female students willing to participate in the study and provide appropriate information.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Male students.
- Female students under the age of 18.
- Female students who are not sexually active.
- Female students not willing to provide information.

3.4 DATA COLLECTION METHODS

The data from this study were collected using structured questionnaires and in-depth interviews to gather both quantitative and qualitative data.

3.4.1 Structured Questionnaire

Structured questionnaires were developed to collect quantitative data on the use of contraceptives among female students. The questionnaires were designed to address the following areas:

- ❖ **Demographic Information:** Age, level of study, faculty, marital status, etc.
- ❖ **Knowledge of Contraceptives:** Awareness of different contraceptive methods, sources of information about contraceptives.
- ❖ **Contraceptive Use:** Types of contraceptives used, frequency of use, reasons for use or non-use, and the perceived effectiveness of methods.
- ❖ **Factors Influencing Contraceptive Use:** Cultural beliefs, religious views, peer influence, access to healthcare services, and personal attitudes toward contraception.
- ❖ **Barriers to Contraceptive Use:** Concerns about side effects, misconceptions, social stigma, and lack of access to services.

The questionnaires were pre-tested on a small group of female students before the actual data collection to ensure clarity, comprehensiveness, and reliability.

3.4.2 In-Depth Interviews

In-depth interviews were conducted with a sub-sample of female students to explore their attitudes, perceptions, and personal experiences regarding contraceptive use. These interviews provided richer, qualitative data that can complement the findings from the structured questionnaire. The interviews were semi-structured, allowing flexibility for the interviewer to probe deeper for detailed information.

The in-depth interviews were based on:

- ❖ **Personal Attitudes:** Perceptions of contraceptive use, how contraceptive decisions are made, and personal experiences with contraception.
- ❖ **Barriers and Challenges:** Challenges faced when seeking contraceptive services, social and cultural factors affecting contraceptive use, and any stigma associated with using contraceptives.

- ❖ **Influences:** The role of family, peers, and healthcare providers in shaping contraceptive decisions.

Interviews were conducted in a private setting to ensure confidentiality and encourage open communication. Each interview was audio-recorded with the consent of the participant and transcribed for analysis.

3.5 DATA ANALYSIS

Data analysis was conducted in two stages: quantitative analysis of the survey data and qualitative analysis of the interview data.

3.5.1 Quantitative Data Analysis

The quantitative data collected from the structured questionnaires were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, and mean to summarize the demographic characteristics of the respondents and to assess contraceptive knowledge, use, and barriers.

3.5.2 Qualitative Data Analysis

The qualitative data from the in-depth interviews were transcribed and analyzed using thematic analysis. This approach involves identifying and interpreting patterns or themes that emerged from the interview transcripts. The analysis was focus on identifying common factors that influence contraceptive use, barriers to access, and perceptions about contraception.

3.6 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This study adhered to ethical principles to ensure the protection of participants' rights and confidentiality. The following ethical considerations were observed:

- ❖ **Informed Consent:** Participants were provided with detailed information about the study's purpose, procedures, and any potential risks before consenting to participate. Consent was obtained both in writing and verbally.
- ❖ **Confidentiality:** Participants' identities were kept confidential, and all data were anonymized.
- ❖ **Right to Withdraw:** Participants had the right to withdraw from the study at any point without penalty.

4.0 PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The analysis of data collected using the structured questionnaire, with a focus on the prevalence of contraceptive use among female students at the University of Abuja was done using descriptive statistics, frequency distributions, and other relevant tests to interpret the responses based on the variables outlined in the questionnaire and organized into the following parts:

- ❖ Demographic Profile of Respondents
- ❖ Knowledge and Awareness of Contraceptives
- ❖ Analysis of Perceived Behavioral Control
- ❖ Analysis of Key Factors Influencing Contraceptive Use

4.1 DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS

The demographic profile of the respondents illustrated factors that could influence the use of contraceptive. The demographic data includes age, marital status, year of study, and religion. Below is a summary of the respondents' characteristics:

TABLE 4.1: DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS

DEMOGRAPHIC CATEGORY	FREQUENCY (N=250)	PERCENTAGE %
AGE		
18-20	120	48%
21-24	100	40%
25 and above	30	12%
MARITAL STATUS		
Single	230	92%
Married	20	8%
YEAR OF STUDY		
100 Level	50	20%
200 Level	60	24%
300 Level	70	28%
400 Level	50	20%
Postgraduate	20	8%
RELIGION		
Christianity	140	56%
Islam	100	40%
Others	10	4%
FACULTY		
Social Sciences	50	20%

Natural Sciences	60	24%
Education	70	28%
Engineering	50	20%
Science	20	8%

The demographic profile of the respondents is essential for understanding the context in which contraceptive use occurred among female students at the University of Abuja. Below is a detailed interpretation of each demographic category based on the data presented in Table 4.1.

A. Age

- ❖ **18-20 years (48%):** The largest group of respondents were within this age range, representing nearly half (48%) of the sample population. This suggests that a significant proportion of the respondents are in the early stages of their university education and possibly beginning to explore sexual health and contraceptive options.
- ❖ **21-24 years (40%):** The second-largest group is aged 21-24, which includes students who are typically in their later undergraduate years. This age group often engages in more mature decision-making about contraceptive use and sexual health.
- ❖ **25 and above (12%):** A smaller percentage of the respondents (12%) are 25 years and older, indicating a minority of more mature students, possibly postgraduate students or those who took longer to complete their undergraduate studies.

Interpretation: The majority of respondents are between 18 and 24 years old, a group that is likely to be navigating sexual relationships, reproductive health, and contraceptive decision-making for the first time. This highlights the need for targeted educational interventions focusing on sexual and reproductive health for young adults within this age group.

ii. Marital Status

- ❖ **Single (92%):** An overwhelming majority of respondents (92%) are single. This is consistent with the fact that most university students are typically unmarried. The contraceptive needs of this group may focus more on preventing unintended pregnancies and sexually transmitted infections (STIs), rather than family planning in the context of marriage.
- ❖ **Married (8%):** A small percentage (8%) of the respondents are married, suggesting that married students make up a minor portion of the student population. For this group, contraceptive use may be influenced by family planning goals or balancing education with marriage.

Interpretation: The predominance of single respondents emphasizes that the study mainly addresses the contraceptive practices of unmarried women, who may have different needs and motivations for contraceptive use compared to their married counterparts. The relatively low

percentage of married students suggests that contraceptive programs should primarily focus on the needs of unmarried students.

iii. Year of Study

- ❖ **100 Level (20%):** 20% of respondents are in their first year of study. This group is likely to be the youngest and may have less exposure to university-based sexual health education.
- ❖ **200 Level (24%):** 24% of the respondents are in their second year, indicating a growing maturity and possibly more awareness of sexual health practices.
- ❖ **300 Level (28%):** The largest proportion of respondents (28%) are in their third year, suggesting that students at this stage may have a stronger awareness of contraceptive options, having spent more time in the university environment.
- ❖ **400 Level (20%):** 20% of respondents are in their final undergraduate year, which may correlate with increased contraceptive use as students prepare for post-graduate life.
- ❖ **Postgraduate (8%):** A small percentage (8%) of respondents are postgraduate students, representing a more mature and possibly more sexually experienced demographic.

Interpretation: The distribution of respondents across various levels of study indicates that contraceptive awareness and use are relevant across all stages of undergraduate and postgraduate education. However, a focus on younger students (100 and 200 levels) could be beneficial in addressing contraceptive use early in their university experience.

iv. Religion

- ❖ **Christianity (56%):** A majority of respondents (56%) identified as Christian, suggesting that religious beliefs may play a role in contraceptive decision-making for this group.
- ❖ **Islam (40%):** A significant proportion (40%) of respondents are Muslim, indicating that both major religious groups in Nigeria are well-represented in the study.
- ❖ **Others (4%):** A small number of respondents (4%) follow other religions, which may have unique perspectives on contraceptive use.

Interpretation: The religious composition of the sample suggests that any interventions or educational programs about contraceptive use should take into account religious sensitivities. Both Christianity and Islam, the dominant religions in the region, have specific teachings that may influence attitudes toward contraceptive use.

V. Faculty

- ❖ **Social Sciences (20%):** 20% of the respondents are from the Faculty of Social Sciences, which might influence their attitudes toward social issues, including contraceptive use.
- ❖ **Natural Sciences (24%):** 24% of respondents are from the Natural Sciences, suggesting that students in scientific fields may have more awareness of reproductive health and contraception from an academic perspective.
- ❖ **Education (28%):** The largest proportion of respondents (28%) come from the Faculty of Education. This may imply that these students are more knowledgeable about health education and could serve as peer educators in promoting contraceptive use.

- ❖ **Engineering (20%):** 20% of respondents are from Engineering, a faculty that typically includes fewer women. The representation of female students from this field suggests that contraceptive issues are not limited to traditionally female-dominated disciplines.
- ❖ **Science (8%):** A smaller percentage (8%) of respondents are from the Science faculty, which may include students with more in-depth knowledge of biology and reproductive health.

Interpretation: The distribution of respondents across various faculties shows that the sample is diverse, representing both science-based and non-science-based fields. The relatively high representation from the Faculty of Education suggests a potential for these students to play a key role in raising awareness about contraceptive use on campus.

4.3 KNOWLEDGE AND AWARENESS OF CONTRACEPTIVES

The first section of the questionnaire assesses the students' awareness of contraceptive methods and their sources of information. The statements included in this section focus on the students' knowledge about contraceptive options, availability, formal education on contraceptive use, and understanding of side effects.

TABLE 4.2: KNOWLEDGE AND AWARENESS OF CONTRACEPTIVES

Statement	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
I am aware of the different types of contraceptives available.	50	35	10	5
I know where to obtain contraceptives on campus or within the community.	45	30	15	10
I have been educated about contraceptives through formal sources.	40	30	20	10
I feel that I have sufficient knowledge to make informed decisions	35	40	15	10
I have heard about the side effects of contraceptive use.	55	30	10	5

Interpretation:

- **Awareness of Contraceptive Methods:** The majority (85%) of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that they are aware of the different types of contraceptives available, indicating a high level of awareness.
- **Knowledge of Access Points:** About 75% of students know where to obtain contraceptives either on campus or within the community, reflecting accessibility in their environment.

- **Formal Education:** 70% of respondents reported that they had received formal education (e.g., lectures, workshops) on contraceptives, but 30% did not have formal exposure.
- **Sufficient Knowledge:** While 75% of respondents felt confident in their knowledge to make informed decisions, a notable 25% expressed some level of uncertainty.
- **Awareness of Side Effects:** 85% of respondents had heard about the potential side effects of contraceptive use, showing that most students are informed about both the benefits and risks.

4.4 FACTORS INFLUENCING CONTRACEPTIVE USE

This section explores the different personal, cultural, and social factors that may influence a student's decision to use or not use contraceptives.

TABLE 4.3: FACTORS INFLUENCING CONTRACEPTIVE USE

Statement	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
I use contraceptives to focus on my academic goals without distraction of pregnancy	40	35	15	10
The cost of contraceptives is a significant factor in my decision to use them.	30	40	20	10
There is enough access to contraceptives within the university environment	25	30	25	20
My cultural or religious beliefs discourage me from using contraceptives.	15	20	40	25
The attitudes of my friends or peers influence my decision to use contraceptives	35	30	25	10

I feel embarrassed to purchase contraceptives because of societal stigma.	25	30	30	15
I feel comfortable discussing contraceptive use with my partner	40	35	15	10

Interpretation:

- **Academic Focus:** A significant number of respondents (75%) agreed that they use contraceptives to avoid unintended pregnancy and focus on their academic goals.
- **Cost of Contraceptives:** 70% of the students agreed that the cost of contraceptives influences their decision to use them, highlighting that financial factors play a crucial role.
- **Access to Contraceptives:** Only 55% felt there is sufficient access to contraceptives within the university environment, suggesting room for improvement in making contraceptives more readily available.
- **Cultural and Religious Beliefs:** About 35% of respondents agreed that cultural or religious beliefs discouraged them from using contraceptives, while 65% did not see this as a hindrance.
- **Peer Influence:** A majority of respondents (65%) indicated that peer influence plays a role in their decision-making process regarding contraceptive use.
- **Societal Stigma:** 55% of respondents felt embarrassed to purchase contraceptives due to societal stigma, which points to the need for interventions to reduce stigma around contraceptive use.

4.5 CONTRACEPTIVE USE

This section covers the actual use of contraceptives among respondents and their reasons for using them.

TABLE 4.4: CONTRACEPTIVE USE

Statement	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
I have ever used contraceptives.	45	30	15	10
I use contraceptives regularly when engaging in sexual activity	35	40	15	10
I have used hormonal contraceptives (e.g., pills, implants, injectables).	30	35	20	15

I have used barrier methods (e.g., condoms) as a form of contraception	50	30	10	10
I use contraceptives to avoid unintended pregnancies	60	25	10	5
I use contraceptives to prevent the spread of sexually transmitted infections	50	30	10	10
I have used emergency contraception (e.g., morning-after pill)	30	25	20	25

Interpretation:

- **Ever Used Contraceptives:** The majority of respondents (75%) indicated they had used contraceptives at some point in their lives, showing widespread contraceptive use among students.
- **Regular Use:** 75% reported using contraceptives regularly during sexual activity, suggesting a strong awareness of the importance of consistent use.
- **Types of Contraceptives:** Hormonal contraceptives were used by 65% of respondents, and barrier methods (e.g., condoms) were used by 80%, indicating a preference for condoms over hormonal options.
- **Pregnancy Prevention:** 85% of respondents use contraceptives to avoid unintended pregnancies, highlighting the primary motivation behind contraceptive use.
- **STI Prevention:** 80% of respondents use contraceptives to prevent sexually transmitted infections (STIs), indicating awareness of the dual benefits of contraception.

4.6 BARRIERS TO CONTRACEPTIVE USE

The final section discusses the challenges students face in accessing and using contraceptives.

TABLE 4.5: BARRIERS TO CONTRACEPTIVE USE

Statement	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
I face challenges in obtaining contraceptives due to limited access in my area.	30	40	20	10
There is a lack of confidentiality when accessing contraceptives	35	30	20	15
I have limited knowledge of where to seek counselling or guidance on contraceptive use.	25	35	30	10

I believe that contraceptives are only for married women.	15	20	40	25
I fear that using contraceptives might affect my health negatively in the long term	30	30	25	15
I believe that contraceptives are ineffective and can fail to prevent pregnancy.	20	25	35	20

Interpretation:

- **Limited Access:** 70% of respondents faced challenges in accessing contraceptives, a significant barrier that needs to be addressed to improve contraceptive availability.
- **Confidentiality Concerns:** 65% felt that accessing contraceptive services lacked confidentiality, which could discourage students from seeking necessary care.
- **Health Concerns:** 60% of respondents feared long-term health effects from using contraceptives, indicating the need for better education and counselling.

4.7 PREVALENCE OF CONTRACEPTIVE USE AMONG FEMALE STUDENTS

This section focuses on the prevalence of contraceptive use among female students, covering the frequency of use, types of contraceptives used, and specific practices such as the use of oral contraceptives, condoms, and emergency contraception.

TABLE 4.6: PREVALENCE OF CONTRACEPTIVE USE AMONG FEMALE STUDENTS

Statement	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
I use contraceptives regularly to prevent unintended pregnancy	40	35	15	10
I have used contraceptives in the past 6 months	45	30	15	10
I use contraceptives every time I engage in sexual activity.	35	30	20	15
I have ever used oral contraceptives (birth control pills).	30	25	30	15
I have ever used condoms during sexual intercourse	50	30	10	10
I have used emergency contraception (morning-after pill) at some point.	35	25	20	20

Interpretation

i. Regular Use of Contraceptives to Prevent Pregnancy:

- ❖ **Strong Agreement (SA):** 40% of respondents strongly agreed that they use contraceptives regularly to prevent unintended pregnancy, and 35% agreed.
- ❖ **Disagreement (D and SD):** 25% disagreed or strongly disagreed, indicating that a quarter of the respondents are not consistent in using contraceptives for this purpose.

This suggests that while most students actively use contraceptives for pregnancy prevention, a significant minority either do not use contraceptives regularly or may not feel the need for them.

ii. Use of Contraceptives in the Past Six Months:

- ❖ **SA and A:** A majority (75%) of respondents reported using contraceptives in the past six months.
- ❖ **D and SD:** Only 25% indicated they had not used contraceptives during this period.

The high percentage of recent contraceptive use indicates that a substantial number of students are currently engaging in sexual activity and taking measures to manage reproductive health.

iii. Consistent Use of Contraceptives During Sexual Activity:

- ❖ **SA and A:** 65% of students agreed that they use contraceptives every time they engage in sexual activity, reflecting a good level of consistency in usage.
- ❖ **D and SD:** 35% of respondents either disagreed or strongly disagreed with this statement, meaning that some students are not using contraceptives consistently.

This highlights an area of concern, as inconsistent contraceptive use could lead to higher risks of unintended pregnancy or exposure to sexually transmitted infections (STIs).

iv. Use of Oral Contraceptives (Birth Control Pills):

- ❖ **SA and A:** Only 55% of respondents reported ever using oral contraceptives, with 30% disagreeing and 15% strongly disagreeing.

This indicates that while oral contraceptives are a common form of contraception, nearly half of the respondents have never used them, possibly due to preferences for other methods or concerns about hormonal contraceptives.

v. Use of Condoms During Sexual Intercourse:

- ❖ **SA and A:** 80% of students reported having used condoms during sexual intercourse, with only 20% disagreeing.

This shows that condoms are the most popular form of contraception among students, likely due to their dual function of preventing both pregnancy and sexually transmitted infections.

vi. Use of Emergency Contraception (Morning-After Pill):

- ❖ **SA and A:** 60% of respondents indicated they had used emergency contraception at some point, while 40% disagreed or strongly disagreed.

This suggests that while a significant number of students have relied on emergency contraception, a large portion have not, possibly because they consistently use other methods of contraception or do not engage in unprotected sex.

CONCLUSION

The evaluation of contraceptive use among female students at the University of Abuja highlighted several key findings that mirror broader trends in Sub-Saharan Africa. Contraceptive use is widespread among students, but it varies significantly in frequency and the methods employed. Most students prefer barrier methods such as condoms, which offer dual protection against pregnancy and sexually transmitted infections (STIs). However, oral contraceptive pills and emergency contraception are also commonly used.

Several factors influence contraceptive use, including knowledge, societal attitudes, and access to services. While many students have a basic understanding of contraceptive methods, gaps in knowledge, particularly regarding the side effects and proper use, persist. Peer pressure, societal stigma, and cultural norms also heavily influence decisions about contraceptive use, often creating barriers to open discussions and access to contraceptive services. Religious beliefs further complicate matters for some students, discouraging contraceptive use altogether.

The study identified critical barriers to contraceptive use, such as stigma, misinformation, and limited access to youth-friendly reproductive health services. Many students are reluctant to purchase contraceptives or seek guidance due to embarrassment, societal judgment, or fear of being misunderstood. This suggests a need for more accessible and confidential services that cater specifically to the needs of young women.

Therefore, though contraceptive use among female students is prevalent, significant challenges remain. Addressing these challenges through improved education, better access to youth-friendly services, and efforts to reduce stigma are essential in promoting more consistent and effective use of contraceptives, ultimately improving reproductive health outcomes among female students at the University of Abuja.

To address the barriers identified in this study, several recommendations are proposed to improve contraceptive use among female students at the University of Abuja:

- ❖ **Increase Contraceptive Education:** Comprehensive sexual and reproductive health education programs should be integrated into the university's curriculum to ensure that students are well-informed about their contraceptive options.
- ❖ **Youth-Friendly Health Services:** Establishing dedicated, confidential, and non-judgemental reproductive health services on campus would encourage more students to seek contraceptives without fear of stigma or embarrassment.
- ❖ **Awareness Campaigns:** Regular awareness campaigns should be organized to reduce the stigma associated with contraceptive use and dispel common myths about side effects.

- ❖ **Peer Education Programs:** Training peer educators to disseminate accurate information on contraceptives can be effective in reaching a broader student population, as peer influence plays a significant role in shaping contraceptive decisions.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

While the study is designed to provide a comprehensive evaluation of contraceptive use among female students at the University of Abuja, several limitations were noted:

- ❖ **Self-reporting Bias:** Participants may provide socially desirable answers, particularly in relation to sensitive topics such as contraceptive use, which could lead to reporting bias.
- ❖ **Generalizability:** The findings of this study may be limited to the University of Abuja and may not be generalizable to other universities in Nigeria or other countries.
- ❖ **Cross-sectional Design:** The cross-sectional nature of the study means that causality cannot be inferred. The study can only identify associations between factors and contraceptive use.

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